

Harmful Algae News

AN IOC NEWSLETTER ON TOXIC ALGAE AND ALGAL BLOOMS

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United Nations
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Intergovernmental
Oceanographic
Commission

International Conference on Harmful Algal Blooms and Desalination

The First International Conference on Harmful Algal Blooms and Desalination was held in Muscat, Oman on April 17-18, 2014. This conference was organized to identify the knowledge gaps that heighten the concerns and challenges to sustainable production of drinking water by desalination in areas subject to harmful algal blooms (HABs).

In many arid regions, countries are increasingly reliant on seawater desalination to supply drinking water for rapidly growing coastal populations. There are currently more than 14,000 desalination plants in more than 150 countries worldwide. In 2008, the installed capacity was 52.3 million m³/d. The desalination market is expected to grow by 12% per year reaching a capacity of 94 million m³/d by 2015.

An emerging threat to the desalination industry is from HABs. In recent years, toxic or high-biomass blooms have caused serious impacts on the operation of desalination plants, in part because of an expansion in the number

of HABs in some regions and in part because of the transition from thermal desalination to reverse osmosis (RO), the treatment process that is most affected by HABs. Impacts include the cessation of operations due to clogging of filters, fouling of surfaces, damage to RO membranes, as well as taste and odor problems. In the case of toxic HABs, there has been concern that toxins could persist in the treated water and thus represent a threat to human health [1]. Recent evidence suggests that these toxins should largely be excluded during freshwater production with suitable pretreatment [2] well-maintained membranes or with other desalination procedures such as multi-stage flash evaporation [3]. However, not all toxins have been assessed, and the breakthrough of some low molecular weight organic compounds (e.g., taste and odor components) has occurred, so it is unclear whether toxin exclusion under operational conditions is universal. The concern is that even low-level

Fig. 1 Omani government officials at the opening session for the HABS and Desalination Conference, Oman, April 17-18, 2014.

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Fig. 2 Two of the three Co-Chairs of the Conference: Don Anderson, WHOI, and Shannon McCarthy, MEDRC

toxin penetration into treated waters, if persistent, could be a chronic exposure threat to human health.

A recent HAB of the dinoflagellate *Cochlodinium* is a clear example of the risk posed by these phenomena. That outbreak, which lasted over 8 months in the Arabian Gulf-Arabian Sea region [4], closed or restricted the operation of multiple desalination plants, one for as long as 55 days. With little reserve water storage or alternative sources, this was a major threat to the region.

The initial impetus for the conference came in part from the IOC's Intergovernmental Panel on HABs (IPHAB), which passed a resolution recognizing the problem and the need for an international conference. IPHAB appointed Don Anderson to lead the effort and appointed a scientific steering committee with representatives from multiple countries. Concurrently, and independently, the Middle East Desalination Research Center (MEDRC) recognized the importance of this issue and held a small workshop in 2012 that also set the stage for the 2014 conference.

The two-day conference had 130 participants from 18 countries. This was the first major meeting to bring HAB experts together with desalination scientists, engineers and operators, as

well as government officials responsible for water supply and public health. Toxic and high biomass HABs are increasingly common in the Arabian/Persian Gulf, Gulf of Oman, and the Red Sea as well as many other areas of the world where desalination occurs, and these restricted basins also are experiencing greater eutrophication and other anthropogenic stresses, making Oman an ideal setting for an inaugural meeting on this topic.

Held under the patronage of H.E. Mohammed al-Mahrouqi, Chairman of the Public Authority for Electricity and Water (PAEW), Oman, the conference was co-chaired by Don Anderson (Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution), Shannon McCarthy (Middle East Desalination Research Center) and Hamed Al Hasni (PAEW). The meeting had a number of corporate and public sponsors and multiple partner organizations and media partners. The complete list of sponsors, as well as the program, are available on the MEDRC website: <http://www.medrc.org/home/habd/>.

The meeting began with background presentations on HABs and on desalination to help all participants understand basic concepts. Then, through a combination of invited and contributed

talks, sessions were convened on dissolved and colloidal organic materials, pretreatment processes, desalination plant design and operations, HAB distribution and dynamics, HAB control, and technologies for HAB detection and forecasting. The conference concluded with a plenary discussion that addressed research priorities and that also highlighted the strong consensus for another meeting on this topic, probably in two-three years. Research needs can be broadly categorized as those leading to improved operational practices at desalination plants, and forecasting of HAB effects. These two categories overlap in that better knowledge about the underlying causes of operational problems (e.g., membrane fouling) will help inform about the conditions that must be forecast. The research priority summary will be presented to the IPHAB at its next meeting in 2015.

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This publication presents the first summary of our knowledge of benthic dinoflagellate species. Information on the book content, instructions for purchase, etc can be found at: <http://www.schweizerbart.de/publications/detail/isbn/9783510614028/Kle>

International Workshop on the Ecology and Taxonomy of Benthic Marine Dinoflagellates: Project Report

Inspired by the GEOHAB Open Science Meeting on HABs in Benthic Systems, a Workshop on the Ecology and Taxonomy of Benthic Marine Dinoflagellates was held in Malaysia in May 2012. This Core Research Project was sponsored by GEOHAB-IOC and funded to commemorate the "Living Ocean and Coast" theme of the Expo 2012 in YEOSU ("beautiful water"), Korea. This multiyear project incorporated:

- a hypothesis driven field effort,
- followed by a taxonomic workshop,
- a number of individual project proposals to implement sampling in different habitats as a proof of concept for a new sampling method and
- a reporting session culminating in presentations at WESTPAC in April 2014 and a publication on BHAB collecting methods.

With the recent resurgence of interest in the BHABs, there is a concern that the lack of a standardized sampling protocols reduces the potential for meaningful comparison between studies [1]. Benthic harmful algae bloom (BHAB) species occupy complex habitats. Some can be found on a variety of substrates, for example turf algae, macrophytes, sea grasses or on coral rubble and in sand. The objective of the field effort and workshop was learn to identify BHAB species and to compare sampling protocols for benthic species. Both natural and artificial substrates were tested in a number of different habitats.

Existing sampling protocols for BHABs included: (a) collecting substrates in plastic bags and dislodging cells of interest by shaking, then normalizing the resultant cell counts on a per gram wet or dry weight basis [2-3],

(b) scraping turf algae off substrates into collection tubes and normalizing the final cell counts to surface area or removing cells from substrate surfaces using suction devices (slurp guns) or vacuum systems, and normalizing final cell counts to surface area [4] and (c) placing artificial substrates, such as pieces of fiberglass screen, in benthic habitats to collect cells with subsequent recovery of cells via shaking and filtration [5]. One of the core research projects identified by the GEOHAB-BHAB Report [1] is a quantitative evaluation of sampling methods. Of particular interest is whether estimates obtained from collecting cells from natural substrates (macrophytes) are comparable to those obtained from artificial substrates. To begin addressing this issue, the workshop, *Ecology and Taxonomy of Benthic Marine Dinoflagellates*, was held in Malaysia 21-31 May 2012. Dr. Gires Usup from the National University of Malaysia and Dr. Patricia Tester, National Centers for Coastal Ocean Science, National Ocean Service, NOAA, lead sixteen participants in a field exer-

Fig. 1. Participants in GEOHAB International Workshop on the Ecology and of Benthic Marine Dinoflagellates, 21-31 May 2012, Malaysia. First row, seated, left to right: Dr. Leaw Chui Pin, Dr. Lim Po Teen, Dr. Mitsunori Iwataki, Prof Dr. Sharim Ahmad, Dr. Wayne Litaker, Prof Dr. Gires Usup, Prof Dr. Mazlan Ghaffar, Dr. Asmat Ahmad, Dr. Patricia Tester, Dr. Jacob Larsen, Dr. Normawaty Mohd Noor, Middle row, standing from left to right: Jeeva Moganarajo, Moime Walican, Hikmath Thoha, Intan Ernieza Farhana, Nguyen Ngoc Lam, Grace Joy Chin Wei Lie, Grace Abdala, June Moh Hwei Yieng, Hua Zhang, Nguyen Ngoc Tuong Giang, Ho Van The, Gan Hui Shan, Mimi Nora Mansor, Sitti Ryah, Berdiri Barisan Belakang, Top row, standing, from left to right: Shereen Yim, Nguyen Chi Thoi, Praderm Uttayarnmanee, Arief Rachman, Gan Jia Cheng, Mark Skinner, Hong-Chang Lim, Hii Kieng Soon, Tan Toh Hii, Teng Sing Tung, Thamrin Thamrin

cise to compare BHAB sampling methods (Figs 2-4).

The group departed Kuala Lumpur for a six hour bus ride to reach the southeast coast of Malaysia at Johor. Then a short boat ride to the field base on Tinggi Island provided an ideal location to test the hypothesis, "Are benthic HAB species and the cell abundances collected on artificial substrate correlated with benthic HAB species and cell abundances collected on adjacent macrophytes?" A week of field work provided data to test the hypothesis as well as material to examine during the second week of the course at the National University of Malaysia. There Drs. Gires Usup, R. Wayne Litaker, Jacob Larsen, Mitsunori Iwataki, Lea Chu Pin, Lim Po Teen and Normawaty Mohd Noor lectured on the taxonomy of BHAB species especially *Gambierdiscus*, *Prorocentrum*, and *Ostreopsis*. During this second week the field participants were joined by twelve others; all were introduced to the molecular techniques currently used in BHAB species identification (Fig. 5) [6].

Preliminary results indicated a positive correlation between the species and cell abundance collected on the artificial substrate and natural substrate (macrophytes). At the conclusion of the workshop the participants were invited to write proposals that would allow them to test the artificial substrate sampling method back in their coastal areas and compare BHAB species and cell abundances found on natural substrates like macrophytes. Successful proposals were submitted by Hikma Thoha and Thamrin Thamrin from Indonesia, Lim Po Teen, Normawaty Mohd Noor and Gires Usup from Malaysia, Ho Van The from Vietnam and Lu Song Hui, Peoples' Republic of China. Their collective results are being assembled for analysis, report-out and discussion in a web-facilitated session planned for March 2014. To date a manuscript using the artificial sampling method taught in the workshop has been published [7] and a methods manuscript incorporating the study results [8]. Abstracts from the IOC-GEOHAB-YEOSU Project were submitted to the WESTPAC meeting 22-25 April 2014 in Nha Trang, Vietnam for presentation of the project results. Project related publications are:

- Tan, T.-H., P.-T. Lim, A. Mujahid, G. Usup, C.-P. Leaw. 2013. Benthic harmful dinoflagellate assemblages in a fringing reef of Sampadi Island, Sarawak, Malaysia. *Marine Research in Indonesia* 38 (2) 11-21.

Fig. 2. Sampling off Tinggi Island (W. Chris Holland, Steven R. Kibler and Gan Jia Cheng).

Fig. 3. Sample preparation (Steven R. Kibler and workshop participants).

Fig 4. Field cell counting stations (Teng, Sing, Hikmah Thola and Arief Rachman).

Fig. 5. Arief Rachman, Praderm Uttayarnmanee and Hii Kieng Soon examining the morphology of BHAB dinoflagellates in the laboratory of Prof. Usup at the Universiti Kebangsaan.

- Tester, P.A., S.R. Kibler, W.C. Holland, G. Usup, M.W. Vandersea. C.-P. Leaw, P.-T. Lim, J. Larsen, M. Mohammad-Nor, M.A. Faust and R.W. Litaker. 2014. Sampling harmful benthic dinoflagellates: Comparison of artificial and natural substrate methods. *Harmful Algae* 39:8-35.

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NF-POGO AWI-CofE Regional Training Programme

Detection of HABs in Southeast Asia by Remote Sensing: Operational Warning and Regional Monitoring Protocols

Harmful algal blooms, HABs, represent a concern in Southeast Asian (SEA) countries particularly where the frequency and severity of HAB occurrences have increased with anthropogenic factors such as eutrophication and climate change. HABs are associated with a variety ecosystem impacts, e.g., fish kills as well as financial impacts, e.g., bans on shellfish harvests. The causes and consequences of HABs vary from country to country, yet a common set of detection methods and protocols exist that could be implemented, regardless of the region, for the detection of HAB events in the early stages as well as for the development of an early-warning system. Remote sensing data and integrated modelling, combined with holistic monitoring programmes specific for each country, provide an operational framework for a set of protocols that can be implemented in each region to help understand and detect HAB events, enabling appropriate mitigation and management responses.

In response to these broad needs, an intensive hands-on three-week training programme was offered to students with basic or no prior experience with satellite remote sensing and modelling techniques. This was held at the Bolinao Marine Laboratory, Pangasinan, Philip-

pinos of the Marine Science Institute, University of the Philippines from 24 February to 15 March 2014. The programme provided the students with a fundamental interdisciplinary knowledge of HAB dynamics, capability to assess HAB sites using satellite remote sensing technology, design of standardized monitoring protocols, initial skills and tools to begin to develop integrated HAB models, and assistance in the development of an early-warning system for HABs in their own countries.

Twenty-four trainees were selected from a large number of applicants. These participants came from six countries: India (3), Indonesia (4), Malaysia (3), Philippines (9), Thailand (1), and Vietnam (4).

The local organizers and hosts of the Philippine Regional Training Programme were Drs. Aletta T. Yñiguez and Laura T. David from the Marine Science Institute, University of the Philippines, Diliman (MSI-UPD). Mr. Joseph Dominic Palermo and Mr. Aldwin Almo, also from MSI-UPD, also supported the Training Programme as did Dr. Rhodora V. Azanza (MSI-UPD), who provided organizational input as well as HAB biology expertise.

Five local scientists from MSI-UPD who are actively investigating HABs

through the Department of Science and Technology-funded programme on HABs in the Philippines provided their time and expertise: Drs. Cesar L. Villanoy, Gil Jacinto, Maria Lourdes San Diego-McGlone, Fernando P. Siringan, and Mr. Chris Mendoza. International experts in HABs, remote sensing and modelling shared their expertise: Dr. Kazumi Matsuoka from Japan, Dr. Chui Pin Leaw from Malaysia, Dr. Stewart Bernard from South Africa, Dr. Liew Soo Chin from Singapore and the Drs. William Cochlan and Raphael Kudela from the USA. Dr. Gerald Plumley, a representative from the Centre of Excellence in Observational Oceanography (CofE)-AWI also attended the training programme.

The CofE at the Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Center for Polar and Marine Research, was the main external sponsor of the Philippine Regional Training Programme; the CofE-AWI is sponsored by and supported through Nippon Foundation – Partnership for the Observation of the Global Oceans (NF-POGO).

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Dr. William Cochlan conducting a hands-on activity for the chemical oceanography of HABs module.

Group photo at the end of the three week training.

IOC Qualifications in Identification and Enumeration of Harmful Microalgae

Since 1993 the IOC has conducted training courses in identification/taxonomy and enumeration of harmful microalgae. The advanced course held at Uni-

versity of Copenhagen includes 100 hours of teaching and is divided into two parts, an internet part consisting of 50 hours of teaching prior to the prac-

tical part also consisting of 50 hours of teaching. The first part of the course is an internet teaching programme mainly for self-study of background material of the various groups of harmful algae, while the second part is a practical course in species identification. The course finishes with a 3-hour practical examination in species identification which qualifies for an IOC CERTIFICATE OF PROFICIENCY IN IDENTIFICATION OF HARMFUL ALGAE. Certificates are issued to participants who have at least 70% correct answers.

This year's practical course was held 12-21 August and the participants came from Colombia, Costa Rica, El Salvador, Hong Kong, Jamaica, México, Nicaragua, South Africa, Spain and the United Kingdom and was an engaged and hard working group enjoying the wisdom and guidance of Jacob Larsen, Santiago Fraga, Øjvind Moestrup, Nina Lundholm and Helene Annadotter.

IOC Training Course on Harmful Marine Microalgae 2014

News

Only four weeks before the next 16th International Conference on Harmful Algae in Wellington, New Zealand!

There are more than 400 participants already registered and an exciting programme you can check on-line. Go to the ISSHA website (www.issha.org) and directly to the conference website to get more information on invited speakers, social events, etc.

The 15th ICHA Proceedings

These will be published as: Kim, H.G., B. Reguera, G. Hallegraeff, C.K Lee, M.S. Han and J.K Choi. (eds). Harmful Algae 2012, Proceedings of the 15th International Conference on Harmful Algae. International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae 2014, ISBN 978-87-990827-4-2. (All the accepted manuscripts are on line on the ISSHA website)

ISSHA Council Elections

Deadline for nominations for a new President and Secretary and replacing Council members is on 26th September. ISSHA members can vote on line.

Venue for the 18th ICHA Conference (2018)

Bids have been presented from France and Germany to host the 18th ICHA in 2018. ISSHA members will be able to vote on-line and/or during the conference in New Zealand after listening to the bids presentations on Monday 27 October.

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International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae

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An exceptional *Dinophysis* driven toxic algae event in the Scottish Shetland Islands

Fig. 1. *Dinophysis* from field populations in the Shetlands. A. *Dinophysis acuta*; B. *Dinophysis acuminata* complex

Harmful algal blooms (HABs) of the genus *Dinophysis* are common in UK waters (Fig. 1), and are spatially and temporally variable, with marked differences between years. In common with other EU shellfish harvesting countries, human health is protected by regulatory monitoring of both the concentration of toxins within the shellfish flesh and the abundance of the potentially causative biotoxin-producing phytoplankton in the water column. In Scotland the regulatory authority is the Food Standards Agency, with the phytoplankton component of the monitoring being conducted by SAMS Research Services Limited (SRSL), the commercial arm of SAMS.

Historically, there have been a number of UK human health incidents linked

to *Dinophysis* mediated diarrhetic shellfish poisoning (DSP). For example in June 2006, 171 people became ill after consuming mussels from a Scottish site [1].

In general, and certainly in recent years, monitoring has been very successful in preventing contaminated shellfish from reaching market. However, during the summer of 2013, 70 people in London and the South East of England contracted DSP after consuming mussels (*Mytilus edulis*) harvested in the Shetland Islands, Scotland (Fig. 2). The mussels had been supplied to a number of restaurants, some through a number of intermediary suppliers. Customers reported illness after eating at: Belgo in Covent Garden, Holborn, Clapham and Bromley; Zero Degrees in Blackheath and Reading; The Phoenix near Hook, Hampshire; Boulevard Brasserie in Covent Garden; and Pig's Ears in Richmond. The vast majority of cases occurred between 13th and 15th July. While there were no known severe or long-lasting health impacts, the negative impact of the

Fig. 2. Map of location showing sampling sites mentioned in the text.

event for the industry was significant, making headlines on both local and national news.

Although the numbers of *Dinophysis* observed in the waters around Shetland had exceeded the regulatory monitoring programmes warning levels for several weeks preceding the event, toxicity testing indicated concentrations of biotoxins, although finite and rising, were below the regulatory threshold.

Two days after the event, however, the monitoring programme indicated that its numbers had risen very rapidly to unexpectedly large values in the waters around the islands, with associated high shellfish toxicity. Action was immediately taken to suspend operations in the area but, unfortunately, not before one of the farms harvested and shipped some of the affected mussels. While this incident was exceptional, it is instructive to analyse the causes behind it and determine whether current early warning methods could be improved.

In summer, regulatory monitoring occurs weekly, a frequency that is typically sufficient to give one or two weeks warning of the increase in harmful algal cells to densities above regulatory threshold that may result in shellfish toxicity. However, in summer 2013 the rate of increase in *Dinophysis* abundance in the Shetland Islands was unprecedented, going for example at one site, from 340 (cells/l) to 6,280 (cells/l) in the space of only one week (Fig. 3).

A plot of the median *Dinophysis* abundance value for each day of the year (for the period 2006 to 2013) demonstrates that the 2013 bloom markedly exceeded that in previous years in terms of magnitude (Fig. 4), with a Chi Square test showing that this difference was significant. This rapid increase, to an exceptionally high abundance, resulted in an increase of shellfish toxicity from a below threshold value of 150 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$) recorded at Muckle Roe on 3rd July to a value markedly above threshold of 3,452 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$) by 10th July.

The observed rapid increase in cell abundance was greater than that which could be explained by *in situ* growth alone, and hence we examined other potential environmental factors that might have caused the rapid bloom development. As *Dinophysis* can happily grow in dynamic, offshore locations such as a shelf front [2], it was decided

Fig. 3: Plot of *Dinophysis* abundance increasing with time.

Fig. 4: *Dinophysis* counts recorded in Shetland during 2013 (circles) plotted against median values of *Dinophysis* recorded in Shetland between 2006 and 2013 (solid black line). Dashed lines represent the 5th and 95th percentiles of the data collected between 2006 and 2013.

to look at the local wind patterns. Data was obtained from the British Atmospheric Data Centre (BADc) [3], and used to create a climatology of mean wind directions in Shetland between 2006 and 2013. When compared with the wind direction observed during the summer of 2013 it was noticed that, while the usual mean, prevalent wind direction during June, July and August is from the South East, during the summer of 2013 the wind direction changed and blew predominantly from the West. This suggested that the large numbers of *Dinophysis* observed were blooming out at sea and then being carried into the bights and voes of Shetland where they were accumulating.

Rigorous monitoring is still the safest way to ensure that consumers can eat shellfish with confidence and without worrying about food poisoning.

However, as the recent toxicity event illustrates, the possibility for contaminated shellfish to enter the food supply still exists. While phytoplankton monitoring picked up the 2013 event, a sampling frequency of at least bi-weekly would have been required for the rapid rise in biotoxins to have been spotted in time for appropriate action to be taken.

Given the costs and logistical difficulties of such high frequency monitoring, this is not a viable option for the future. Rather, enhanced early warning methodologies are required. To this end SAMS are currently producing weekly "bulletins", first developed within the EU FP7 project ASIMUTH (www.asimuth.eu) that provides a summary of the current HAB/biotoxin status of the area and risk assessment of the likelihood of harmful blooms in the following week. Inclusion of wind data in these bulletins

allows the local industry to better assess the risk of future rapid wind driven HAB events (Fig. 5).

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Fig. 5: Example of a page of the Shetland bulletin with the wind rose.

An unprecedented bloom of *Gonyaulax polygramma* in Kota Kinabalu, Sabah, Malaysian Borneo

The west coasts of Sabah, northern Malaysian Borneo, have been experiencing harmful algal blooms annually for the past four decades since the first incident of paralytic shellfish poisoning (PSP) was reported in 1970 [1]. Since then, harmful algal monitoring has been undertaken by governmental agencies (Fisheries Research Institute, and The Department of Fisheries, Sabah) to safeguard seafood safety, in particular in shellfish mollusks harvested from the region. Seasonal blooms in the area were always found to be associated with the highly toxic dinoflagellate *Pyrodinium bahamense*. The blooms, however, occasionally were followed by unarmored harmful dinoflagellates, *Cochlodinium polykrikoides* and *Gymnodinium catenatum* [2].

In a field survey conducted in April 2014, we observed a bloom of a heavily thecated dinoflagellates with maximum cell densities of $9 \pm 0.36 \times 10^5$ cells L⁻¹. The bloom was found to form patches between the southern part of Sepanggar Island and eastern Gaya Island (Fig. 1).

Fig. 2. Light and epi-fluorescence micrographs of *Gonyaulax polygramma*, bar = 10 μ m.

Based on light and epi-fluorescence microscopic observations, the dinoflagellate was identified as *Gonyaulax polygramma* (Fig. 2). *G. polygramma* blooms were previously reported in Japan [3], South Africa [4] and the South Sea of Korea [5], but there were no previous records from Southeast Asia. Some *Gonyaulax* species are known to produce yessotoxin (YTX), i.e. *G. spinifera* that caused YTX contamination in green-shell mussels (*Perna canaliculus*) in New Zealand [6]. Despite well-studied

bloom-forming harmful marine dinoflagellates in Kota Kinabalu, this represents to our knowledge the first record of a *G. polygramma* bloom accompanied by water discoloration in the area (Fig. 1). Fortunately neither fish kills nor intoxicated shellfish were reported during this bloom.

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Fig. 1. (a) Sampling sites at northwest Kota Kinabalu coast. Dotted circle indicates blooms location. (b) Blooms forming patches [arrow]. (c) Red discoloration. (d-e) Research scientists collecting water samples using plankton net and Van-Dorn water sampler.

First report of *Pyrodinium bahamense* cysts in marine sediments from the Gulf of Fonseca, El Salvador

Fig. 1. *Pyrodinium bahamense* cysts. Micrographs of specimens found at the 0-2 cm section in core GF01 at 32X (A-B) and 40X (C) taken with a manual camera.

The PSP toxin producer *Pyrodinium bahamense* has been reported in tropical and subtropical estuaries and coastal areas from the Atlantic and western Pacific oceans [1]. Dense blooms of this species, reaching concentrations up to $106 \text{ cells} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$, have been reported in Malaysia [2], Papua New Guinea, The Philippines, Guatemala and Costa Rica [3, 4]. *Pyrodinium bahamense* poses a threat to public health and the exploitation of artisanal fisheries in El Salvador, a country with an economy that largely relies on coastal resources for its subsistence. Blooms of this species have reached densities of $3.3 \cdot 10^4 \text{ cells} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$ in April 2010 [5]. Further blooms occurred in August 2011, with $1.4 \cdot 10^4 \text{ cells} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$ and a toxicity of $1872 \mu\text{g equiv STX} \cdot 100\text{g}^{-1}$, and in September 2012, with $730 \mu\text{g equiv STX} \cdot 100\text{g}^{-1}$ detected

in oysters and death of sea turtles associated with the event [5].

The Gulf of Fonseca ($13^\circ 15' \text{ N}$, $87^\circ 45' \text{ W}$) covers an area of about $3,200 \text{ km}^2$ with a coastline that extends for 261 km of which 185 km are in Honduras (northwest and east), 40 km in Nicaragua (south), and 29 km in El Salvador (northwest). During March and August 2012, fifteen sediment cores were collected at the Gulf of Fonseca, El Salvador to look for the occurrence of dinoflagellate cysts following the method of Matzuoka and Fukuyo [7]. Samples were collected with an Uwitec A-5310 gravity corer at an average depth of 8 m. Cyst analyses were carried out of the top 10 cm of each core sample subdivided in 5.2 cm thick transversal slices. A total of 75 core sediment samples were sonicated using a Branson Sonifier 450 and

sieved through 125 and $20 \mu\text{m}$ meshes. Analyses were performed at the Marine Toxins Laboratory of the University of El Salvador (LABTOX-UES).

Thirteen cysts of *Pyrodinium bahamense* were detected in 6 out of 15 sediment cores, confirming the occurrence of the most recurrent producer of toxic (PSP) HABs in the study area. The cysts, with a mean diameter of $48 \mu\text{m}$, had a pale or transparent wall, a cytoplasm with yellowish granules and a lateral red spot that was used as a taxonomic criteria (Fig. 1). This is the first report on the occurrence of *Pyrodinium bahamense* cysts in coastal waters from El Salvador.

In addition, 178 cyst morphotypes, belonging to the genera *Protoperidinium*, *Pyrodinium*, *Scrippsiella* and *Alexandrium*, with a maximum concentration of 31 and 40 cysts $\cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$ (in cores GF07 and GF14 respectively), were found in the top 10 cm of sediment (Fig. 2). Of these, 7 were identified at species level. Species cyst reported for the first time in El Salvador were *Protoperidinium subinerme*, *Stelladinium reidi*, *Protoperidinium oblongum*, *Protoperidinium conicoides*, *Protoperidinium sp1* (Fig. 3, 4).

Only one specimen of the genera *Alexandrium* and *Scrippsiella* were found. Further cyst analyses in samples collected along the coasts of El Salvador are needed. The low density of *P. bahamense* cysts found in Gulf of Fonseca casts doubts on whether these act as inoculum of the blooms. Dense patches of the dinoflagellate were detected offshore in 2009 before a PSP event affected coastal shellfish resources [8].

Fig. 2. Dinoflagellate cysts density (cysts $\cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$) in core sediment samples from the Gulf of Fonseca, El Salvador.

Fig. 3. Frequency (%) of the most abundant species found on the top 10 cm in sediment cores from the Gulf of Fonseca.

Fig. 4. Micrographs of other species cysts found in samples collected at the gulf of Fonseca: A) *Protoperidinium subinermis*; B) *Stelladinium robustum*; C) *Protoperidinium oblongum*; D) *Protoperidinium conicoides*; E) *Protoperidinium* sp; F) *Alexandrium* sp; G) *Scrippsiella* sp and H) *Protoperidinium* sp.

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Forthcoming Events

11th Advanced Phytoplankton Course - Taxonomy and Systematics
Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn (SZN), Naples, Italy, 4-24 October 2015. Contact: Adriana Zingone (zingone@szn.it). Application form at <http://www.szn.it>

PICES 2014 Annual Meeting, Yeosu, Republic of Korea, 16 - 26 October 2014. HAB-Section Meeting 18 October. Contact: Vera L Trainer (vera.l.trainer@noaa.gov)

16th International Conference on Harmful Algae (16th ICHA), Wellington City, New Zealand, 27-31 October 2014. <http://www.icha2014nz.com/>

COI/FANSA Curso avanzado de entrenamiento sobre microalgas marinas nocivas: Biología y Toxicidad. Chubut, Argentina, 10 - 22 November 2014. Contact: Martha Ferrario (meferra@fcnym.unlp.edu.ar)

ICES - IOC Working Group on Harmful Algal Bloom Dynamics (WGABD), Lisbon, Portugal, April 2015 (t.b.c.) Contact: Eileen Bresnan (Eileen.Bresnan@scotland.gsi.gov.uk)

12th Session of the IOC Intergovernmental Panel on Harmful Algal Blooms (IPHAB), UNESCO, Paris, France, 21-23 April 2015 (t.b.c.) Contact: Henrik Enevoldsen (h.enevoldsen@unesco.org)

Bloom of *Dolichospermum flos-aquae* in a coastal lagoon in the Southern Gulf of Mexico

Fig 1. Map of Alvarado lagoon and location of sampling station (in red).

Alvarado lagoon (Fig. 1) is a coastal lagoon permanently connected to the Gulf of Mexico. This lagoon has a mean salinity of 5.59 psu [1]. The low salinity values are due to the influence of many important rivers that discharge into the lagoon which is the final part of the watershed called Papaloapan, one of the most important watersheds in Mexico. The mean salinity may decrease in the rainy season due to increased rain and riverine inputs.

At the beginning of October 2013, discoloured water (yellowish) was noticeable in most of the area of Alvarado lagoon. On October 3rd 2013, a water sample was obtained from the surface at the site called "Arbolillo", 10 km distance from Alvarado City (Fig. 1). The sample was fixed with acetate-lugol. Counting of filaments and cells was done using a Sedgwick-rafter chamber.

The species that caused the water discoloration was *Dolichospermum flos-aquae* (Brébisson ex Bornet & Flahault) P.Wacklin, L.Hoffmann & J.Komárek (synonym: *Anabaena flos-aquae* Brébisson ex Bornet & Flahault) (Fig. 2). Counting chains resulted in 1938 filaments ml^{-1} . Based on the mean number of cells per filaments, a cell density of 91357 cells ml^{-1} was estimated. No other phytoplankton species occurred except *Phacus* sp. with a density of 2 cells ml^{-1} . Chains of cells (filaments) formed regular-irregular spirals and

were composed of 5-217 cells (mean=47.14, n=86). Cells were spherical with a diameter of 4.9 μm or slightly constrained in the center (maybe due to cellular division). Heterocysts occurred in variable number and in long filaments we observed from 3 to 5. Akinetes were not observed.

Salinity when the bloom occurred was 2 psu and temperature was 28°C. Although Alvarado lagoon is an oligohaline-mesohaline system, during August-September 2013 the lagoon received an unusual amount of freshwater. In addition to the rainy season, two tropical depressions affected Veracruz coasts and the Central States of Mexico. The tropical storm "Fernand" caused more than 200 mm of rain in August 24-26th; hurricane "Ingrid" hit North of Veracruz on September 16th, and brought rain throughout the region with values of 100-150 mm in the center and south of Veracruz. Papaloapan River is one of the most important rivers of Mexico and discharges into Alvarado lagoon. This river and others caused a noticeable increment in the level of Alvarado lagoon.

This is the first report of a bloom of this cyanophyte in Alvarado lagoon,

Fig 2. *Dolichospermum flos-aquae* specimen from Alvarado Lagoon, Mexico (scale bar = 10 μm).

although in a similar system close to it, *Dolichospermum flos-aquae* caused a rare bloom in 2006. We believe that that the unusual rainfall in this year is a factor that contributed to the bloom in Alvarado. The Papaloapan watershed comprises the states of Puebla, Oaxaca and Veracruz, and agriculture is one of the main economical activities in the watershed. The lower watershed is subject to flooding every year [2] in the rainy season, and this is enhanced by tropical depressions, so most of the fertilizers drain into Alvarado lagoon during this period. The tropical depressions "Fernand" and "Ingrid", besides bringing an unusual fresh water supply, might have increased the availability of nutrients in the lagoon and thus favoured the *Dolichospermum flos-aquae* bloom.

Alvarado lagoon is an important region for shrimp and oyster fisheries in Mexico [3] and because of the discoloration of water, sanitary authorities established vigilance those days. No toxic effects were recorded in the lagoon, nor in the community of Alvarado, but it is known that *Dolichospermum flos-aquae* produces toxic microcystins and nodularins [4, 5]. Because of the occurrence of this potentially toxic species in a bloom, caution is important in the detection of future water discoloration in Alvarado lagoon.

Acknowledgements

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Which Lugol's is the best 'solution'?

Lugol's iodine solution (Lugol's) is generally recognised as being the most suitable preservative to use when studying phytoplankton taxa, in part because it is less toxic than alternatives such as formaldehyde and glutaraldehyde [1]. Each preservative is more suited to a different range of taxa but in general Lugol's is preferred for most 'wild' samples. Table 1 shows three different versions of Lugol's which we decided to compare against each other to determine which might be best used to preserve various phytoplankton taxa.

From April 2013 to February 2014 we conducted a series of degradation experiments on a range of algal species, specifically chosen to represent a wide range of taxon groups.

For each representative species, the sample was homogenised and divided equally into three subsamples which had been spiked with 2ml of L_{acid} , C_{acid} or C_{neut} . The mean count of cells in three 5ml aliquots of each sample were enumerated after 1 day of preservation using the Utermöhl technique [2]. This process was repeated after 3 days, 1 week, 2 weeks, 1 month, 2 months, 4 months, 6 months and 8 months.

The comparative degradation of cell counts in each Lugol's solution was highly variable across the different species tested. Figures 1 and 2 are revealing examples of the variability found.

The full results of these experiments are currently been prepared for publication. It is already apparent that L_{acid} , C_{acid} or C_{neut} may each be the most or least efficient Lugol's preservatives, depending on the taxa being studied. Determining the overall 'best' solution may prove very difficult, the 'lag time' between preservation and analysis is certainly a key factor in this decision.

It is clear that due to the lack of peer reviewed papers comparing the different Lugol's solutions; further work in this area will be of great utility to those conducting monitoring programmes or working with data derived from preserved samples.

Acknowledgements

We thank Dr. R. Pipe and M. Jutson of The Plymouth Culture Collection, Marine Biological Association, Citadel Hill,

Figure 1: Results of Prorocentrum lima experiment

Figure 2: Results of Ditylum brightwellii experiment

Table 1: Details of Lugol's solutions used

Preservative name	Source	Concentrations
Lab Acid (L_{acid})	Produced 'in lab' by Cefas staff	8% potassium iodide / 4% iodine / 8% concentrated acetic acid / 84% distilled water
Commercial Acid (C_{acid})	Purchased commercially	0.68% potassium iodide / 0.34% iodine / ~98.98% distilled water / <1% acetic acid
Commercial Neutral (C_{neut})	Purchased commercially	0.68% potassium iodide / 0.34% iodine / 98.98% distilled water

Plymouth, PL1 2PB, UK and D. Sivyer, Dr. V. Creach, R. Beckett, C. Crisp, S. Milligan, N. Travell and A. Walton of Cefas.

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Introducing a web-based interactive identification key to species of *Pseudo-nitzschia* (Bacillariophyceae)

Fig. 1. A page from the web site on interactive identification of *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp

Pseudo-nitzschia is one of the most important genera of harmful algae because of the ability of some species to produce the neurotoxin domoic acid, responsible for amnesic shellfish poisoning (ASP) [1, 2]. This diatom genus is distributed worldwide [3, 4], with 44 valid species currently described [5]. Identification of *Pseudo-nitzschia* species relies heavily on minute differences in ultrastructural features on the diatom frustule. However, this morphometric information can only be obtained by advanced electron microscopy, including transmission electron microscopy (TEM). In addition, complexes and varieties of *Pseudo-nitzschia*, including cryptic species (that are morphologically identical, or too similar to be distinguished, but genetically different) and pseudo-cryptic species (that have minor ultrastructural differences) continue to be discovered, making species identification difficult.

Here we present a comprehensive taxonomic database of the 44 valid species and two varieties (*P. pungens* var. *cingulata* and *P. pungens* var. *aveirensis*) of *Pseudo-nitzschia* (total of 46 taxa) and an interactive key for species identification (Fig. 1), <http://imperialis.inhs.illinois.edu/dmitriev/key.asp?key=Bacillariales&lng=En&i=1&keyN=2>. This web-

based interactive key was created using the 3I (Internet-accessible Interactive Identification Key and the Taxonomic Database Software Package) [6]. This interactive key is designed to assist researchers in identifying *Pseudo-nitzschia* species. An alternative computer-assisted identification of *Pseudo-nitzschia* species, not available on the Internet, was designed by Ehrman and Kaczmarek [7].

The database contains 18 morphological characters, grouped into four aspects of the diatom frustule: 1) poroids; 2) fibulae and striae; 3) valve; and 4) cingular band (the valvocopula) (Fig. 1) [8]. Half of the morphological characters are numerical, based on morphological measurements; the others are multiple-state characters. Examples of each of these characters are obtained by clicking on a link, where the character states are defined and micrographs illustrate how to measure the numerical characters. In addition to taxonomic information, this web-based database also gives the species' global distribution and a list of literature references.

The main window of the interface presents the list of characters, with a drop-down box of a set of states (Fig. 1). Species identification may start with any character by choosing a state from the drop-down box. Each character has a hyperlink to illustrative images. The <Proceed> button is then pressed after the states of one or several characters have been chosen. This will update the list of taxa fitting the search criteria, and display a list of "Eliminated taxa" and "Characters useful/no longer relevant for further identification". If a character has multiple states and there is uncertainty about which one to choose, the "not" box can be checked (Fig. 1); the taxa not having this state will remain in the list. For characters with nu-

meric values, the range of valid values is shown in square brackets.

An exciting auto-generated function, <Compare>, is available to compare two or more species. <Compare> features include illustrative "Images"; "Similarities"; "Differences"; "All Characters"; and "Diagnosis". A phenetic tree of selected taxa of *Pseudo-nitzschia* can be reconstructed using the complete linkage method of cluster analysis. Finally, the interface links to the NCBI databases Taxonomy Browser and GenBank.

This web-based interactive key to species of *Pseudo-nitzschia* provides a taxonomic database platform to assist species identification. The species list, global distribution, and literature references will be updated periodically. The interactive key and database are at the beta-test stage, and under-going validation. This key can also be accessed from www.harmfulalgae.info/psn.html, where one can find more detailed instructions. Please direct feedback, with any queries or comments, to Sing Tung Teng (tst861208@hotmail.com) or Chui Pin Leaw (cpleaw@um.edu.my).

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Red Tides dissemination in Ushuaia, Argentina, an area with record observations of PSP toxicity

This could be just another story about raising awareness on the red tides phenomenon. It tells you how a group of experts from the southernmost tip of the American continent, when changing their dissemination work strategy, met the most moving learners from our society, the kids.

Here we are in the city of Ushuaia, capital of the province of Tierra del Fuego (Argentina). Ushuaia is by the Beagle Channel, the place where the first fatal case of paralytic shellfish poisoning within the Yamanas aborigines was reported by Dr. Polidoro Seguers in 1886. Cases of shellfish poisoning were not reported again until summer 1991-1992, when record levels of PSP toxins in shellfish (127,000 µg STXeq/100gr) were estimated in association with a bloom of the dinoflagellate *Alexandrium catenella*. Since then, the Marine Environment Laboratory from Tierra del Fuego carries out a monitoring for the presence of shellfish toxins in the Beagle Channel region. Population awareness-raising activities (dissemination talks, seminars, expositions, brochures) started about 5 years ago. Our activities were not always welcome, there was not a genuine interest to learn and sometimes people even questioned the existence of PSP events in the Beagle Channel.

As an alternative, we decided to create characters representing different shellfish vectors of the toxins to present them in an attractive manner to kids. This initiative developed and ended with the creation of a "Red Tides" comic which is currently used for dissemination schools and educational centres in the whole province (see the comic, in English and Spanish, in the following pages). We started our first visits to kindergartens and primary schools in Ushuaia feeling hesitant about how our new educational tool would be received. With pride and delight we realized we had succeeded to strike deep into the children's mind. Children amazed us with their open minds about a subject that turned out to be so complex for many grownups. For them it was a

simple and amusing story! Half an hour talking, drawing, writing and having fun was enough to make parents go the next day to the school to ask what their kids had been learning about. It was such a positive experience, that in some cases the school children wanted to continue studying about red tides with the participation of their parents, the same ones that had stared at us before as if we were weird creatures. Some of the children's work were presented at provincial and national science fairs and even received prizes for their excellent results. We attach our "Red Tides

Comic" (English and Spanish). We hope our experiences are of interest to you. Greetings from the end of the world!

Information on the Yamanas tribes and Tierra del Fuego can be found at the World's End Museum (Museo del Fin del Mundo) website www.mfm-ushuaia.com.ar.

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Fig. 1. Les Éclaireurs lighthouse, Beagle Channel, Argentina

THE RED TIDE PHENOMENON

BEAGLE CHANNEL

THE RED TIDE PHENOMENON BEAGLE CHANNEL

The productivity of the sea increases and thousands of microscopic algae reproduce so rapidly, that they may change the colour of sea water to yellow-brown or red.

Spring is starting in the southernmost part of the continent and a strange phenomenon begins in the waters of the Beagle Channel

At the same time, mussels feed by filtering these algae, dragged by current...

It's a very small dose, but it will be fatal to human beings if they consume that...

It is a natural cycle for mollusks. Our friend the mussel had enough algae... but he does not realize that these algae produce a dangerous toxin... of course it doesn't matter, because the toxin does not alter its shape or colour...

This phenomenon is called red tide and occurs at some moments of the year when mollusks show a high level of toxicity...

...if they are not properly controlled by sanitary authorities...

This can be very dangerous for people

Something terrible is about to happen...

Within 5 to 30 minutes a fatal intoxication occurs. In moderate cases, there is a slight tingling and numbness around the mouth, headache, dizziness and nausea. If the intoxication is severe, it can cause death.

The culprit...

Alexandrium catenella

a phytoplankton (microscopic algae) that lives in the waters of Beagle Channel and produce a toxin that affects the following shellfish...

MUSSEL

CLAM

LIMPET

OYSTER

SCALLOP

Fresh mussels are often collected by local producers for commercial purposes...

All of them take their products to the Laboratory of Marine Toxins and Microbiology of Ushuaia...

to be analysed

laboratory staff take a sample for testing...

in order to analyze the presence of paralytic shellfish toxins. Commercial shellfish permits are issued only...

if the levels of toxins are below the established limit for human consumption...

R

If the product is in good condition, the certificate stating that it is fit for human consumption is issued...

The producer can sell his shellfish, always handing in a copy of the certificate of analysis to his clients...

CERTIFICATE
LABORATORY OF MARINE TOXINS AND MICROBIOLOGY
"FIT FOR HUMAN CONSUMPTION"

Now it's done!...

But let's go back for a moment to the *Alexandrium catenella*...

Until autumn comes back and the water gets cold again...

To understand the red tide phenomenon, we must know the natural cycle of the *Alexandrium catenella*, which begins here, on the sea bed...

...He goes to the surface and produce a large scale bloom...

...The *Alexandrium* returns to the depths, to its resting cyst...

...Until the spring, when the sun shines more brightly and the temperature gets warmer...then he wakes up...

During winter the *Alexandrium catenella* remains sleeping under the mud on the sea bed, protected by a cyst, (a sort of capsule).

When the reproductive cycle is completed, he falls asleep again...

In the meantime, at the hospital...

Always remember!!!

CONSUME SAFE SHELLFISH, CERTIFIED BY THE LABORATORY OF MARINE TOXINS AND MICROBIOLOGY OF USHUAIA.

Oh!, I was so lucky... Next time I buy mussels I will ask for the certificate...

IDEA Y GUIÓN: EQUIPO DEL LABORATORIO.

THE END

**EL
FENOMENO
DE
LA**

**MAREA
ROJA**

®

DIBUJOS
NAHUEL
MIERES

¿QUE ES LA MAREA ROJA?

La primavera está llegando al extremo más austral de Sudamérica y un fenómeno comienza producirse en las aguas del canal Beagle

Sube la productividad y miles de diminutas algas microscópicas tóxicas se reproducen rápidamente coloreando a veces el mar con leves tonos pardos, amarillos o rojizos...

En estos momentos muchos mejillones aprovechan para alimentarse filtrando estas alguitas que son arrastradas por las corrientes.

Es un ciclo natural para los moluscos. Nuestro amigo mejillón está satisfecho pues consumió muchas algas... Pero él no se da cuenta de que estas algas producen una peligrosa toxina... ¡Claro, no se entera porque a él no le afecta lo más mínimo, ni le cambia su color o su aspecto!

Es una dosis muy pequeña, pero puede ser mortal si un humano la consume.

Este fenómeno es conocido popularmente como "marea roja" y en las épocas del año en que se producen, los moluscos pueden llegar a las personas con elevados niveles de toxinas...

...si no son controlados debidamente por las autoridades sanitarias...

Algo terrible está por pasar...

El responsable...

Alexandrium catenella

Entre 5 y 30 minutos se produce una intoxicación que si es leve, los síntomas empiezan con un cosquilleo en la boca y a veces vómitos y mareos; si la intoxicación es grave puede llegar a causar la muerte...

un alga microscópica del plancton que vive naturalmente en aguas del Canal de Beagle y produce una toxina que se acumula en los siguientes productos de mar...

Mejillón

Cholga

Lapa

Almeja

Caracol

Periódicamente productores y recolectores de moluscos de la isla cosechan mariscos frescos para su comercialización...

Todos ellos trasladan su mercadería hasta el Laboratorio Regional de Toxinas Marinas y Microbiología de Ushuaia...

...para ser analizada

Un agente del laboratorio toma una muestra representativa de la carga para ser controlada...

...se analiza la presencia de toxina paralizante y solo se permite la comercialización del producto...

...si los niveles de toxinas se encuentran por debajo de límites seguros para el consumo humano...

(R)

Si la mercadería está en óptimas condiciones se entrega el certificado de apto para consumo humano...

El productor sale a vender sus moluscos entregando siempre a los clientes una copia del certificado del análisis...

CERTIFICADO
 LABORATORIO REGIONAL USHUAIA DE TOXINAS MARINAS Y MICROBIOLOGÍA
 "APTO PARA CONSUMO"

¡AHORA SÍ!...

Pero volvamos por un momento a *Alexandrium catenella*...

Hasta que regresa el otoño, el agua vuelve a enfriarse, la luz del sol se debilita...

Para comprender el fenómeno de la marea roja debemos conocer el ciclo de vida de *Alexandrium*, que comienza aquí en el fondo del lecho marino...

...Entonces germina, sube a la superficie y se reproduce a gran escala...

...y *Alexandrium* retorna a las profundidades en forma de quiste...

...Hasta la llegada de la primavera, cuando la luz y temperatura se tornan más agradables... y es allí cuando despierta...

Y cumplido su ciclo reproductivo se duerme nuevamente...

Alexandrium permanece durante todo el invierno bajo el fango del fondo del mar en forma de quiste, una especie de cápsula o "semilla" que le permite dormir tranquilo.

Mientras tanto en el hospital...

Y recuerde siempre!!!

Consumir moluscos seguros certificados por el laboratorio Regional de Ushuaia de Toxinas Marinas y Microbiología

¡Uf que suerte tuve!
 La próxima vez que compre mejillones voy a solicitar el certificado...

IDEA Y GUIÓN: EQUIPO DEL LABORATORIO.

FIN

A Global HAB Status Report

For decades the HAB community and various HAB groups have discussed the need for and the difficulties of a global appraisal of HAB species occurrences and their impacts. In April 2013 the IOC Intergovernmental Panel on HABs (IOC-IPHAB) decided to develop a 'Global HAB Status Report' with the aims of compiling an overview of HAB events and their societal impacts; providing a worldwide appraisal of the occurrence of toxin-producing microalgae; and assessing the status and probability of change in HAB frequencies, intensities, and range resulting from environmental changes at the local and global scale. Linkages will be sought established with the IPCC reporting mechanism which increasingly is focusing on the biological impacts of climate change.

The project now being launched by the IOC, with the support of the Government of Flanders, will compile data on toxic algae occurrence and blooms, focusing on species included in the IOC Taxonomic Reference List/ WoRMS/ HAB (<http://www.marinespecies.org/hab/index.php>). This initiative will happen within the IOC International Oceanographic Data Exchange Programme IODE and its components HAEDAT (<http://haedat.iode.org/>) and OBIS (<http://www.iobis.org/>), in close partnership with the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), the International Council for Exploration of the Sea (ICES), the North Pacific Marine Science Organisation (PICES) and the International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae (ISSHA).

The Project will thus complement and complete global data sets already in OBIS, HAEDAT and WoRMS/ HAB on the distribution and impact of harmful algae with the view to publish an IOC UNESCO Global Harmful Algal Bloom Status

Report. These efforts will take time to complete and we expect it will take up to 2 years to develop the first status report.

There are two main lines of data compilation: species occurrence and HAB events.

For the species occurrence, information will consist of documented records extracted primarily from the published literature. Data will be stored in OBIS. This activity was first introduced several years back in ISSHA and several scientists from around the world volunteered to this in the context of the IOC-ISSHA Project HABMAP. Some have already compiled part or most of the data. However, funding to proceed systematically has not been available until now. We are now in the process of confirming a list of editors for regional data compilations. A monograph in preparation by Lassus et al will be a significant contribution to this effort.

As for HAB events, data are already compiled systematically in some regions and collected in HAEDAT, while a new effort is required for other regions. The collaboration with many agencies and institutions holding monitoring data will be required and we hope for

broad interest and back-up. The new data will also be stored in HAEDAT.

A Task Team established at the last IPHAB meeting (Paris 2013) will oversee the work and develop an outline of the Global Harmful Algal Bloom Status Report (further nomination from IPHAB member states still possible). The Task Team will also recommend a review mechanism; establish a periodicity and a regular process for preparation of a Global Harmful Algal Bloom Report, and for a dissemination and communication strategy. The Task Team is co-chaired by Drs. Gustaaf Hallegraeff (Institute for Marine and Antarctic Studies, University of Tasmania, Australia) and Adriana Zingone (Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn, Naples, Italy).

The first activities in the project work-plan include a training workshop for the researchers who will compile and upload data from each region, organized by IOC in collaboration with IAEA. A side information meeting is also planned at the 16th International Conference on Harmful Algae (ICHA) in Wellington, New Zealand, next October.

If you are more interested, please do not hesitate to contact us at h.eneveldsen@unesco.org

Number of records in OBIS of species that can potentially cause a HAB

- 1 - 1000
- 1001 - 2000
- 2001 - 3000
- 3001 - 4000
- 4001 - 5000

0 1,875 3,750 7,500 11,250 15,000 Kilometers

Lora Fleming awarded with the *Dr Edouard Delcroix* prize

The non-profit organisations HYDRO and the Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ) have established the Dr Edouard Delcroix (1891-1973) Prize in honour of the Belgian orthopaedic surgeon and pioneer in thalassotherapy. This international triennial scientific prize, with a value of 25000 €, is awarded to a researcher or a research team for an original scientific study on the links between oceans and human health (website: <http://www.vliz.be/delcroix>)

In 2013, the IOC and ISSHA nominated Prof Dr Lora E. Fleming, European Centre for Environment and Human Health, University of Exeter Medical School, UK, for the Scientific Prize Dr E. Delcroix 2013. On Friday 27 June 2014 the Hydro VZW and the Flanders Marine Institute VZW, presented in Oostende, Belgium the Prize to Dr. Fleming for her work 'Harmful algal blooms, microbial pollution of marine waters, and climate change beyond the state of the

art (Oceans and Human Health)'.

Prof. Fleming's work over the past decade as both an interdisciplinary physician and epidemiologist in environment and human health, led in the creation of the new scientific discipline of Oceans and Human Health (OHH), bringing together biomedical and oceanographic investigators (including toxicologists, biological/physical oceanographers, health educators, veterinarians, microbiologists, engineers, economists, physicians, and epidemiologists) to do research and training at the frontier in diverse areas: harmful algal blooms, microbial pollution of marine waters, and climate change beyond the state of the art. She was the Director of one of 4 US National Science Foundation (NSF)-National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences (NIEHS) funded interdisciplinary Oceans and Human Health Centres at the University of Miami. In addition to supporting

cutting edge science and training in the modelling of Oceans and Human Health, she has lead several research groups in the area of human exposures and health effects associated with interactions with the oceans and ocean health. Since Jan 2011 she became Director of the European Centre for Environment and Human Health (www.ecehh.org) at the University of Exeter Medical School UK, where she is involved in promoting active engagement in interdisciplinary approaches to the complex challenges of environment and human health.

We congratulate Dr. Fleming with the price and hope to see an increased focus on HABS in the context of Oceans and Human Health (see also 'Message from Betruthan' on pages xx).

H. Enevoldsen/IOC UNESCO

Prof. Dr Lora Elderkin Fleming receives the Prize Dr Edouard Delcroix 2013 © VLIZ (Verhaeghe, Els)

Message from Bedruthan

Unanimous call for a coordinated, transnational and interdisciplinary Oceans and Human Health research programme in Europe

On 20 & 21 March 2014, a group of 50 experts from a broad range of disciplines gathered in Bedruthan (Cornwall, UK) to discuss the complex interactions between the marine environment and human health. The workshop was convened by the **European Centre for Environment and Human Health** (University of Exeter) and the **European Marine Board**, with organizing support from **Ifremer**, the **Scottish Association for Marine Science (SAMS)** and **Plymouth Marine Laboratory**.

Human health and wellbeing are intrinsically connected to the seas and oceans.

This relationship is becoming increasingly important in light of rapidly growing coastal populations and climate change. Europe can achieve significant public health benefits through a better understanding of highly complex marine environment and human health interactions.

Oceans and Human Health – An integrative research field addressing societal needs.

“Oceans and Human Health” (OHH) represents a relatively new and integrative research field, drawing from expertise across the natural, social and economic sciences, including public health and medicine. A beneficial step-change in scientific understanding, evidence-based policy, public awareness and human behaviour is possible through:

- coordinated interdisciplinary research;
- building OHH communities and capacities;
- engaging with stakeholders; and
- managing effective knowledge transfer and science policy interfaces.

The Bedruthan workshop unanimously called for a coordinated, transnational and interdisciplinary Oceans and Human Health research programme in Europe. Research should be solutions-oriented, supporting health and wellbeing promotion and disease treatment, and informing maritime, environment, public health and innovation policy.

European Marine Board (EMB) position paper

The Message from Bedruthan follows publication of EMB position paper 19, “**Linking Oceans & Human Health: A Strategic Research Priority for Europe**”. The EMB is a partnership of 36 major national research institutes and funding agencies from 19 European countries. The paper represents a compelling endorsement from this large European research network of the societal importance for Europe of supporting coordinated interdisciplinary OHH research.

Download at www.marineboard.eu

NEW: “Harmful Algae in the Gulf of Maine: Oceanography, Population Dynamics, and Toxin Transfer in the Food Web”

A special issue on harmful algae in the Gulf of Maine published in May 2014 in *Deep-Sea Research Part II: Topical Studies in Oceanography* (Vol 103). This special issue, available for free downloading until 31 January 2015, consists of 26 papers describing the results of a 5-year multi-investigator research program, Gulf of Maine Toxicity (GOMTOX), formulated and funded through the US-NOAA Ecology and Oceanography of Harmful Algal Blooms (ECOHAB) program. Led by Dr. Donald Anderson at Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution, GOMTOX was a partnership between researchers, federal agencies, state managers, and representatives from the shellfish industry. <http://www.journals.elsevier.com/deep-sea-research-part-ii-topical-studies-in-oceanography/news/free-online-access-to-new-special-issue-on-harmful-algae-in/>

The Gulf of Maine (GOM) in the northwest Atlantic Ocean harbors a valuable shellfish resource that is often impacted by algal blooms of the toxigenic *Alexandrium fundyense* and *Pseudo-nitzschia* spp. responsible for paralytic shellfish poisoning (PSP) and amnesic shellfish poisoning (ASP) respectively. While intensive monitoring efforts and continuous adjustments to harvesting closures in state waters has allowed for the safe harvest of shellfish inshore, vast areas of federal waters offshore had been closed to bivalve molluscan shellfish harvest for decades due to the potential risk of PSP and the lack of understanding of bloom dynamics and associated toxicity in this region. The aim of the GOMTOX was to establish a comprehensive regional-scale understanding of HAB dynamics, transport pathways, and associated toxicity and to use this information and relevant technologies to assist managers, regulators and industry to fully access nearshore and offshore shellfish resources with appropriate safeguards for human health. One of the many noteworthy outcomes from the GOMTOX program was the development of a novel biotoxin manage-

ment strategy that led to the reopening of a portion of Georges Bank to the harvest of bivalves, a multi-billion dollar resource, after being closed for 22 years (<http://www.fda.gov/forconsumers/consumerupdates/ucm368533.htm>). Researchers from the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) led the efforts to: (1) modify PSP test kits for use by fishermen at sea to determine when product was safe for harvest and (2) evaluate the performance of the management strategy via a pilot study that permitted one fishing vessel access to harvest surf clams and quahogs on Georges Bank while following the management strategy, known as the on-board screening dockside testing (OB-

SDT) protocol. Shellfish product landed under the protocol is verified as safe via an approved laboratory method before it is released into commerce.

Success of the pilot study resulted in the safe harvest of \$2.7 million in surf clams in 2010, and in 2013 a region of Georges Bank was reopened for the harvest of shellfish to fishermen that follow the protocol. Access to this fishery has resulted in the doubling of the number of quahogs available on the market and a 40% increase in surf clams.

Interested readers can learn more about the OBSDT management strategy and other GOMTOX project outcomes in the special issue. Scientific themes included in this volume are:

- (1) cysts and sediment dynamics;
- (2) ecology and bloom dynamics;
- (3) the physical/chemical setting;
- (4) toxin dynamics, food web transfer, and monitoring; and
- (5) management implications.

Thanks Tim!

When Harmful Algae News (HAN) was launched in 1992 it was agreed from the start that Tim Wyatt would be the Editor. With the engagement of Tim, the IOC had an experienced editor and serious scientist to help launch and develop the newsletter. In the early days the Editor of HAN was even paid a fee for the work, but over the years this translated into travel support for the ISSHA Conferences, a beer at the ISSHA Conferences and the honour, all as a consequence of the changed framework conditions for IOC and UNESCO. Every second year the IOC has asked Tim about his willingness to take another term and for the past 22 years Tim has been willing to continue. During the spring of 2014 Tim felt it was time to let someone else take over. The IOC Secretariat and all involved with the IOC HAB Programme and IPHAB wish to extend their sincere gratefulness and thanks to Tim for his unusually stable commitment and his efforts which have implied significant time to encourage contributions, help with article writing and editing. It has always been a true pleasure to work with Tim and the manuscripts for HAN have always been delivered with the same high standard of editing. The, at the same time broad and deep, scientific insight of Tim has been very valuable for HAN and his synthetic and personal summaries from several of the ISSHA conferences has been enjoyed and appreciated by the broad HAB community and HAN readers. We hope Tim may still appear as a contributor in HAN. The big question then came, how to find somebody who wished to follow on to Tim? Well, it became clear that there was a wish to have a more formal network of regional-

tors and as these ideas were developed the person that knows Tim better than any, Beatriz Reguera, come up with a model where she and Eileen Bresnan acts as Eds-in-chief and will work with a group of regional editors. After a process of soliciting for volunteers and asking key people we are now proud to introduce the new editor's team for HAN:

Tim Wyatt

Coming deadlines

HAN 50: 15 November 2014
HAN 51: 15 February 2015
HAN 52: 15 May 2015
HAN 53: 15 August 2015

Deadlines to be repeated the following years

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The ambition of the new team is for HAN to become a more regular newsletter, i.e. to appear every 3 months and have fixed submission deadlines for each issue. Also it is the plan in a near future to prepare a HAN index. There are many historic pieces of information that appeared first in HAN and it would be valuable to be able to find and cite them easily.

Please feel free to contact any of the editors if you have article, ideas for article or special issues and we will work with you!

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